

APPLIED PHOTOGRAMMETRY AND REMOTE SENSING FOR ENVIRONMENTAL AND INDUSTRY PHEDCS 2025 TASHKENT

← Submissions

12:30:01pm Asia, Tashkent

Zdeněk Svatý

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Review Results

Contribution Details

Submission Type / Conference Track: Full Paper (Annals)

Presentation Mode: --

Automatic Identification and Vectorization of Traffic Infrastructure Features from Orthophoto Images

Zdeněk Svatý, Pavel Vrtal, Luboš Nouzovský, Jakub Nováček

Organization(s): CTU in Prague, Faculty of Transportation Sciences, Department of Forensic Experts in Transportation Czech Republic

Submitted by: Dr. Zdeněk Svatý (CTU in Prague, Faculty of Transportation Sciences, CZ), ID: 1007

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Topics: 1. Innovative geospatial technologies for the environment, civil engineering, architecture, and mining industry

Keywords: Orthophoto, Road infrastructure, Colour segmentation, Morphological operations, Automation, Vectorization

✓ Full papers submitted for double-blind review must not contain any information which makes it possible to identify the author(s). In particular, name(s) and affiliation(s) must be removed from the manuscript submitted for review. Also sentences such as "As we have shown in previous work (Author_x, 20xx)" are to be avoided. Instead use a formulation such as "Author_x (20xx) has shown ...". Note that submissions which have not been appropriately rendered anonymous may be subject to immediate rejection. In case, the contribution has been accepted for publication, a camera-ready manuscript must be submitted at the due date. In this camera-ready manuscript the name(s) and affiliation(s) of the authors(s) must be identified, and acknowledgements can be personalized.

7 pages

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Review Result of the Program Committee

This contribution has been accepted.

Overview of Reviews

Questions

		Review 1	Review 2
Quality of Content	10%	6	6
Significance for Theory or Practice	10%	6	6
Originality and Level of Innovativeness	10%	6	4
Thematic Relevance for the "Call for Papers"	10%	10	8
Quality of Presentation	10%	10	8
Overall recommendation	50%	9	9
Total points (out of 100)		83	77

Review 1

Evaluation of the Contribution

Quality of Content	Significance	Originality	Thematic Relevance	Presentation	Overall Recommendation	Total points (out of 100)
6 (10%)	6 (10%)	6 (10%)	10 (10%)	10 (10%)	9 (50%)	83

Reviewer's Comments on the Contribution

Contribution of the Submission:

The paper presents a simple MATLAB workflow—color thresholds → morphological filtering → DBSCAN → envelope/skeleton export—and demonstrates statistically significant time savings over manual digitizing ($p = 0.0022$), averaging ~2.15× faster and up to 3.1× on intersection-scale cases.

Comments for the Authors:

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Remarks.

The presented evaluation focuses on speed rather than extraction accuracy/robustness across scenes. Therefore, some points should address extraction accuracy.

Review 2

Evaluation of the Contribution

Quality of Content	Significance	Originality	Thematic Relevance	Presentation	Overall Recommendation	Total points (out of 100)
6 (10%)	6 (10%)	4 (10%)	8 (10%)	8 (10%)	9 (50%)	77

Reviewer's Comments on the Contribution*Contribution of the Submission:*

This paper presents a MATLAB-based method for the semi-automatic identification and vectorization of road markings from orthophotos, using a color segmentation and clustering approach without machine learning. Statistical analysis (paired t-test, $p=0.0022$) confirms the method is significantly faster than manual vectorization, with an average speed increase of 2.15 times (up to 3.1x for complex intersections).

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Recommendations and remarks:

The paper emphasizes automation but also mentions necessary user interventions (e.g., manually removing excess objects post-clustering, merging clusters, defining color tolerances). The term "semi-automatic" is appropriate, but the specific points and degree of user input should be more explicitly detailed in the method section.

The evaluation focuses exclusively on time efficiency (speed), which is a major advantage. However, for the method to be fully validated, the quality of the automated vectorization outputs should also be compared to the manual ground truth.

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